

STYLISTIC EXPRESSIONS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS EXPRESSING HUMAN INTELLECTUAL ABILITY IN ENGLISH

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Abstract: The purpose of this article is to look at the comparative analysis of phraseological units expressing human intellectual ability in the perspective of stylistic aspect and also according to its meaning of stylistic device. Moreover, the role of the stylistic expressions in phraseological units that is representing human intellectual ability in English.

Key words: phraseological units, metaphor, stylistic, stylistic device, allusion, human intellectual abilities, cognitive linguistics.

The term ‘phraseology’ originated in Russian studies which developed from the late 1940’s to the 1960’s. In linguistics, the term ‘phraseology’ describes the context in which a word is used. This often includes idioms, phrasal verbs, and proverbs. “Phraseology is a fuzzy part of language. Although most of us would agree that it embraces the conventional rather than the productive or rule-governed side of language, involving various kinds of composite units and ‘pre-patterned’ expression such as idioms, fixed phrases, and collocations, we find it difficult to delimit the area and classify the different types involved”.

Phraseology is the most vibrant, colorful, and unique aspect of any language's lexicon. In communication, phraseological units can be quite useful. When communicating with others, people utilize words, phrases, and phraseological units to express their thoughts. Phraseological units are figurative sets of expression that are frequently referred to the idioms. Phraseological units characterizing

intellectual qualities a person can be attributed to different stylistic layers of the language. The biggest part of the studied phraseological units refers to the colloquial style of the language, or even to the vernacular (such as a foolish head, a stoerous club, etc.) Also we met phraseological units related to the book style of the English language. Usually, the assignment of phraseological units to one or another style of language is fixed in the dictionary, however, in artistic, journalistic and colloquial speech, we often meet some changes regarding semantics and stylistic reference one expression or another. These changes are especially noticeable if we recall that the properties phraseological units are a well-defined meaning and a constant composition and structure.

However, spontaneous transformations are constantly observed in speech, meanings and forms of phraseological units, due to their functional semantic properties as special expressive units of language nominations that can reflect in their semantic structure the specifics single objects and situations. All contextual transformations of phraseological units are based on their system properties and reveal regular connections between phraseological units as elements of the phraseological system and their speech implementations. Stylistic devices used to enhance expressiveness, modification of the subject-conceptual content phraseological units, lead to occasional transformation of their semantic structure. Consistency and normativity of transformation methods phraseological units, revealed in the aspects of language and speech, is combined with individual-author's, creative realization of them, due to stylistic, artistic and visual functions. In the studies of phraseological units, we observe interest in the topic stylistic transformations of phraseological units. One of the first scientists to study intra-context changes semantics of phraseological units, was A.V. Kunin, who introduced the concepts "usual use" and "occasional use" and analyzed various types of "occasional use" of phraseological units. From this point of view, the scientist distinguishes several types of phraseological configurations:

1. Usual configuration of the first degree, in which phraseological units realize their dictionary meaning, while maintaining stylistic coloring, traditional

structure and component composition. 2. Usual configuration of the second degree, which is characterized by strengthening the stylistic effect within the framework of the inherent stylistic one. 3. Occasional configuration of the first degree, within which there is an occasional transformation of phraseological units due to the use of numerous stylistic devices. 4. Occasional configuration of the second degree, which includes the use of complex stylistic devices. [Kunin 2005, 202] the same the topic is developed in his monograph by E.F. Arsenyeva, highlighting the following types transformations:

1. Replacing the lexical component;
2. Wedging FE;
3. Adding a variable component;
4. Ellipsis. Phraseological allusion;
5. Phraseological repetition;
6. Extended metaphor;
7. Phraseological saturation of the context [Arsent'eva, 2006].

Most scientists are of the opinion that the replacement of lexical component is one of the most common types of contextual transformations. I.B. Golub [Golub 1997] distinguishes the following variants of transformations phraseological units

1. Destruction of the figurative meaning of phraseological units. Reception of destruction figurative meaning of a phraseological unit does not affect the lexicogrammatical composition - its external form is usually preserved, but the meaning is interpreted in a new way.
2. Change in the number of phraseological unit components.
3. Transformation of the composition of a phraseological unit. The renewal of the composition of phraseological units enhances their expressive

coloring, but may or may not affect their meaning. A peculiar stylistic device author's processing of phraseological units is a contamination of several phraseological units. Interesting in our opinion is the work of K.N. Dubrovina [Dubrovina 2005], which analyzes in great detail the methods and techniques of stylistic transformations, highlighting the following ways of using phraseological units: 1. Without transformation: in this case, the stylistic effect occurs in as a result of the interaction of a phraseological unit with the context. In this case, the stylistic effect arises due to the interaction phraseology with context. 1.1. Semantic

paradox -PU collides in the same context with lexico- phraseological units that are not compatible with it in terms of their semantic characteristics. 1.2. A stylistic paradox - in one context, units collide, belonging to different styles of speech and having different stylistic coloring. 1.3. Interaction between two phraseological units in one context or between phraseological units and free phrase when interacting or separate components different phraseological units.

Relationships between interacting components synonymy, antonymy, homonymy, etc. 2. With partial transformation: semantics changes when saving FE forms. 2.1. The use of phraseological turnover in its direct meaning. Here the direct (genetically original) meaning of phraseological units is realized, and the stylistic the effect arises from the use of an external homonym of phraseological units in the context.

2.2. Full alignment (double actualization) - use phrases both in direct and figurative (phraseological) meaning (implementation in one context of both meanings of the phrase). Complete combination is possible only with transformations of the so-called. real PU - which have prototypes in the modern language (phrases whose metaphorization gave FE). 3. With partial transformation: the form of a phraseological unit changes when preserving its semantics.

3.1. Replacing one of the components of a phraseological unit (occasional variant) while the semantics may remain unchanged.

3.2. Expansion of the component composition of PU. Sometimes the extension does not result to a significant change in semantics, but only intensifies it. 4. With a complete transformation of both the form and the semantics of the phraseological unit. 4.1. Changing the semantics of phraseological units when replacing one of the components with a new one, occasional. 4.2. Violation of phraseological impenetrability - expansion component composition of the PU, in which the K.-1. component appears dependent a component that is not part of the PU and returns to the component its direct meaning. As a result of a violation of phraseological impenetrability, a holistic, the undivided meaning of phraseological units is “split” and demetaphorization of phraseological units takes place (its direct

value is returned). After such a transformation, turnover with a direct meaning, homonymous phraseology, and there is a double actualization. 4.3. Contamination of phraseological units: 1) association of phraseological units that have the same component (sometimes - homonymous components), 2) the union of PU-synonyms or PU-antonyms. 1) Combining phraseological units that have the same component (sometimes - components - homonyms). 2) Combining PU-synonyms or PU-antonyms. 4.4. The technique of "phonetic mimicry" - the sound likening of a word or its modified version of other words. Reception is based on partial morpho-phonetic transformation of a component, leading to a complete change semantics of the component and the entire turnover.

1) Replacing one or two phonemes or morphemes with others. 2) Addition (insertion) of one or two phonemes or morphemes. 3) Truncation by one or two phonemes. In all cases of phonetic mimicry, the original PU is the second plan, on the obligatory correlation with which a stylistic effect. 4. Formation of occasional copyright phrases based on popular, usual phraseological units. By degree of similarity / difference copyright phraseological units can be divided into two groups: 1) Replacing a part of the usual phraseological unit with an occasional fragment. Wherein the semantics of phraseological units partially changes: the most broad, generalized meaning, and in the occasional part it focuses narrower, more specific, relevant content.

2) The author uses only the main idea (image, content or individual components) of the original PU. Here the phraseological unit itself as an integral unit is no longer there, but only a general image (allusion) remains. Combined methods of transformation of phraseological units. 5. Extralinguistic means when using phraseological units in stylistic purposes. Extralinguistic means include non-verbal means. communication and information - gestures, facial expressions, drawings, symbolic signs, etc. Combination of proper linguistic and extralinguistic techniques enhances the stylistic effect (caricatures, comic drawings). As a result of the study, the scientist comes to the following conclusions: Some stylistic

devices are inherent in phraseological units as a special unit of the language. Important here:

1) Genetic secondary PU (portability, metaphorical values). This is the basis for the reception of the use of turnover simultaneously and in direct, and figuratively (double actualization).

2) Component composition of a verbal character. Based on this property methods of replacing one of the components with its external homonym (a word in direct meaning), replacement of individual components of a phraseological unit with

occasional units, expansion of the component composition of phraseological units (with the change and preservation of semantics).

3) The constancy of the component composition and structure of the PU and the associated property of the impenetrability of a phraseological unit, the violation of which leads to change in the semantics of turnover and, then, its demetaphorization.

4) Extralinguistic factors (various cultural and historical knowledge of the addressee and various non-verbal means (drawings, gestures, facial expressions, etc.). which are important in case of double actualization of turnover. In the following paragraphs of the third chapter of our study, we will apply development of scientists to our material, consider how various phraseological units, how they are transformed in artistic and journalistic text, in colloquial speech

Expressive - stylistic classification of phraseological units. N.M. Shansky divides the following groups of phraseological phrases with the point of view of their expressive and stylistic properties: [9, 25]

... interstyle

... colloquial

... book

The use of many phraseological phrases is to some extent limited by the framework of a certain style of language (to have mercy on someone - to let the soul go to repentance - belonging to colloquial speech, spring torrents - spring

waters, to go to one's eternal rest - to fall asleep eternal sleep - belonging to the book speech). Many phraseological turns not only name this or that phenomenon of objective reality, but also indicate a certain attitude of the speaker to this phenomenon (disapproval, affection, irony, rhetoric, etc.)

To summarize, stylistic devices and expressive techniques work together to identify the lexical, stylistic, linguistic and extralinguistic approaches that are included in language phraseological units. The stylistic division of phraseological units covers "evaluatively - emotionally expressive characteristics that they acquire (phraseological units) as a result of their preferred and even exclusive use in those rather than other spheres and areas of human communication.

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